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Research Article

**THE STATE OF THE MICROVASCULATURE AFTER
PERFTORAN INFUSION DURING BURN SHOCK****Meylanova R.D.¹, Magomedov M.A.², S.T. Guseinova³, Chilikov V.V.⁴, Dydykin S.S.⁵,
Kruchko P.V⁶**¹PhD, Associate Professor, I.M. Sechenov First Moscow State Medical University (Sechenov University), Operative Surgery and Topographic Anatomy Department, Moscow²MD, PhD, Professor, Dagestan State Medical University, Pathological anatomy Department, Makhachkala³MD, PhD, Professor, Dagestan State Medical University, Human anatomy Department, Makhachkala.⁴Assistant, I.M. Sechenov First Moscow State Medical University (Sechenov University), Operative Surgery and Topographic Anatomy Department, Moscow.⁵MD, PhD, Professor, I.M. Sechenov First Moscow State Medical University (Sechenov University), head of the department of operative surgery and Topographic Anatomy Department, Moscow⁶Assistant, I.M. Sechenov First Moscow State Medical University (Sechenov University), Operative Surgery and Topographic Anatomy Department, Moscow**Abstract**

Thermal burn is a frequent emergency satellite. In a burn, the lymphatic system is involved in the pathological process as well as in any exo (endo) toxicosis with more or less damage to the vital internal organs - the liver, kidneys, lungs, lymphoid structures. First of all, it should be noted the visual signs of a noticeable acceleration of blood flow, which are most noticeable in the resistive and outlet sections of the microvasculature.

Keywords: *perftoran, burn shock, microcirculatory bundle.*

Corresponding author:**Meylanova R.D.,***PhD, Associate Professor,**I.M. Sechenov First Moscow State Medical University,**Moscow*

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INTRODUCTION:

Thermal burn is a frequent emergency satellite. In a burn, the lymphatic system is involved in the pathological process as well as in any exo (endo) toxicosis with more or less damage to the vital internal organs - the liver, kidneys, lungs, lymphoid structures. One of the main pathogenetic links in burn shock is inadequate oxygen consumption, which causes hypoxia and changes in metabolic processes.

The purpose of the study is to study the morphological and functional features of the pathways of the microvasculature in case of burn shock and correction with perftoran.

RESEARCH TECHNIQUE:

The work was performed on white outbred rats of both sexes weighing 150–200 g. Before the experiment, animals were anesthetized by intramuscular injection of a 0.6% Nembutal solution at a rate of 3–5 mg of dry matter per 100 g of weight. For the correction of microcirculation disorders, perftoran (10% emulsion) or saline solution (control) was administered once 60 minutes after the application of the burn injury in the rat femur at the rate of 30 mg per 100 g of body weight. Correction of the microvasculature was observed 6 hours after the control and experimental infusion. Burn disease develops in a pronounced form with superficial burns of more than 25-30% of the body surface and deep burns of more than 10% [2.8]. There are various periodization of burn disease, among which the most common in domestic medicine has received a classification [3,5], including the stages of shock, burn toxemia, septicotoxemia and convalescence. The duration of the burn shock stage is 1–3 days, a 25–30% burn of the body surface of the rat was applied with a 500 W halogen lighting lamp. Thermal burn shock, reproduced by this method, developed after 30 minutes, which corresponds to the data of

modern literature. Investigated the microvessels of the mesentery of the small intestine, the dura mater of the brain and the fibrous capsule of the kidney by impregnation with silver nitrate and the method of vital microscopy. The studied organs differ in their origin and functions, which made it possible to evaluate the effect of thermal injury and its correction in a complex on the whole body. Morphometric measurements on impregnated preparations were performed using a screw-eyed micrometer.

Morphometry made it possible to conditionally divide each link of the microcirculatory bed of all studied objects into two classes of vessels: large and small. The boundary between the classes was the average diameter of the vessels of this microcirculation link. To assess hemodynamics, hemorheology and blood composition, we determined hematocrit level, viscosity of circulating blood, capillary blood flow velocity and blood hemoglobin level. The data obtained were statistically processed using Student's t test.

RESULTS OF RESEARCH:

Six hours after infusion of perftoran in animals with burn shock, positive changes in the architectonics of the vascular networks with their noticeable dilatation and a decrease in the degenerative changes in the vascular wall histostructure were revealed. At the same time, the tortuosity and angulation of microvessels decreased, their distribution was evenly reduced with a decrease in the less vascular zones, and some balance was established between the ways of blood inflow and outflow with changes in the number and type of organization of the vessels. Along with the progressive restructuring of the blood vessels in all studied objects, 6 hours after correction with perftoran, we also found signs of a progressive reorganization of the lymphatic bed. A marked increase in the diameter and a decrease in argyrophilia of the lymphatic vessels (Table 1) were also noted.

Table 1. The diameter (μm) of the main units of the rats' microcirculatory bundle in 6 h after correction by perfluorane infusion (impregnation with silver nitrate; $M \pm m$; $n = 50$)

Structure	Microcirculatory bundle units				
	Arteriole	Precapillary	Capillary	Postcapillary venule	Venule
DM	18.7±0.2	8.5±0.3	5.80±0.07	12.2±0.2	33.7±0.5
MSM	15.0±0.3	9.4±0.1	7.3±0.2	11.9±0.5	18.3±0.4
KFM	21.1±0.1	13.1±0.1	7.0±0.3	17.3±0.6	29.6±0.7

DM – dura mater

MSM – mesentery of small intestine

KFM – fibrous membrane of the kidney

According to biomicroscopy, in a complex of structural changes, meaning a progressive reorganization of the microcirculatory bundle of MSM 6 hours after perftoran infusion, intravascular changes and vascular phenomena characterizing the correction of the functional microangioarchitectonics of the bed draw attention. First of all, it should be noted the visual signs of a noticeable acceleration of blood flow, which are most noticeable in the resistive and outlet sections of the microvasculature.

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